

NOSTRUM

Optimizing Floating Offshore Wind Turbines For Use In The Mediterranean Sea

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*REPORT - SURVEY OF WIND AND SEA
CONDITIONS IN MEDITERRANEAN SEA
AND DEFINITION OF REFERENCE MET-
OCEAN CONDITIONS FOR THREE SITES*

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1. Introduction and Scope

Recent developments in floating wind turbine technology have made offshore wind energy in the Mediterranean Sea a realistic prospect in the near future. In order to minimize Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) and maximize profitability for operators and supply chain alike, ultimately favoring growth in offshore wind energy in the Mediterranean, it is important to understand the met-ocean conditions in this sea basin. This report describes the preliminary survey of met-ocean conditions conducted within the NOSTRUM project.

The survey is conducted at a set of sites in the Mediterranean Sea identified as suitable for offshore wind installations. Indeed, analyzing wind speed is paramount for selecting the appropriate IEC turbine class for blade design. From the survey, three reference sites will be selected to derive and process suitable design load cases for use in the design process.

For each site, the sea state and bathymetry are also verified to assess the proper design load conditions for the Floating Offshore Wind Turbine (FOWT) assembly and to verify the feasibility of an anchoring and mooring system. At this point, the selection will be driven by a reasonable trade-off between the quality of the wind resource and the water depth, i.e., accounting for the technological challenge of achieving an economically sustainable mooring system in very deep waters.

2. Methods

Installation sites are selected based on the criteria detailed in section 3. Once selected, wind speed and direction, significant wave height, mean and peak wave periods information are obtained through the open-source reanalysis database ERA5 [1]. Hourly data spanning from 2003 to 2022 totaling 20 years is considered. The wind speed magnitude at 100m above mean sea water level is aggregated in bins of 0.1 m/s and a Weibull probability density function (PDF) is fit to the raw data.

Table 1: Characteristics of the offshore sites in the Mediterranean Sea

Site	Coordinates	Water depth
Montalto di Castro 1	-42°11'03.03"N 11°20'11.86"E	-126 m
Montalto di Castro 2	-42°15'57.4"N 11°22'39.1"E	-97m
Gulf of Lion 1	-42°56'00"N 3°26'00"E	-90m
Gulf of Lion 2	-43°01'32"N 3°36'58"E	-94m
Malaga 1	-36°15'00"N 4°45'00"W	-874m
Malaga 2	-36°33'01"N 3°15'00"W	-872m
Sicily MedWind	37.7558° N 11.6371° W	-400 m
Sardinia Ichnusa	39.3793° N 8.0369° W	-247 m
Romagna Agnes	44.4296° N 12.6509° E	-70 m
Naples	40° 43' 00" N 14° 10' 00" E	-170 m

15MW and above wind turbines feature hub-heights that exceed 100m. For instance the IEA 15MW RWT features a 150m high hub [2]. The mediterranean rotor that will be developed in this project will likely feature larger swept area to more effectively capture lower wind speeds, and thus a taller tower. Therefore, the wind speed estimate at 100m above sea level extracted from ERA5 may be lower than that experienced by the turbine. In an attempt to more realistically represent the wind speed at turbine hub-height the ERA5-derived value at 100 is scaled using a power law:

$$U_H = U_{100} * \left(\frac{H}{100}\right)^{0.12} \quad (1)$$

Where H is the hub-height of the mediterranean reference rotor designed in the NETTUNO project. Although this design value has not yet been set at this stage of the project, based on the consideration that the rotor will likely feature a larger rotor than the IEA 15MW RWT for increased energy capture at lower wind speeds, H is set to 170m in this document. The exponent of the power law is set to 0.12, as indicated in international offshore design standards [3,4].

3. Survey of potential installation sites in the Mediterranean Sea

Wind speed and direction information is extracted for sites of potential offshore wind development. The sites are selected based on a variety of sources. The main source is [5], from which Figure 1 is derived. A series of offshore wind development areas are shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Offshore wind development areas in west Mediterranean Sea [5]

In order to ensure that a wide range of locations and geographic areas are included in the analysis, the two areas in the vicinity of Malaga are selected – “Malaga1” and “Malaga2” in table 1 – two areas

in the gulf of Lion, geographically located between the French city of Marseille and the Spanish-French border, two sites on the west coast of central Italy – “Montalto di Castro 1 and 2” in table 1 – one site off the southern coast of Sardinia and one off the southern coast of Sicily. All these locations feature deep waters and are thus suitable for floating wind turbines only. In addition to these sites, an additional site in the Adriatic Sea is considered, as an offshore wind project is currently being developed here.

4. Wind and waves conditions in the installation sites

The wind conditions at 100 meters above sea water level are presented in this section.

4.1 Gulf of Lion

Two sites are selected in the gulf of Lion, within French coastal waters in proximity of the city of Perpignan. The Weibull wind speed distribution computed for the two sites at 100m above sea water level is shown in Fig. 3. “Lion 1” features a mean wind speed of 7.14 m/s and a shape factor of 1.67, while “Lion 2” features a mean wind speed of 7.65 m/s and a shape factor of 1.79.

Figure 1. Wind speed distribution, Gulf of Lion

The most significant wave height in these two sites are 0.13 m and 0.56 m respectively, while the mean wave periods are 2.66 s and 2.89 s respectively and the peak wave periods are 1.83 for both sites; instead the mean significant wave height in these two sites are 0.87 m and 0.89 m respectively, while the mean and peak wave periods are 4.8 s and 4.1 s for both sites. The left subplots of the figures below show the distribution of the joint conditions of wave height and wave peak period

(averaging period of 1 hour), colored by the normalized frequency of occurrence in the 20 years of analysis. It is also relevant to verify the conditions of wind-wave misalignment computed as the angle in degree between mean wind direction and mean wave direction. The right subplots of the figures below show the distribution, colored by the normalized frequency of occurrence, of the hourly average wind-wave misalignment per average wind speed.

Figure 2. Sea states and wind-wave misalignment for the site “Lion 1”. The colour map indicates the normalized occurrence frequency

Figure 3. Sea states and wind-wave misalignment for the site “Lion 2”. The colour map indicates the normalized occurrence frequency

4.2 Montalto di Castro

Two installation sites off the Tyrrhenian coast of central Italy have been proposed for Floating Offshore Wind projects. The two sites are called “Montalto di Castro 1” and “Montalto di Castro 2” after the near-by city and industrial hub. “Montalto di Castro 1” features a Weibull wind speed distribution with 6.84 m/s mean and 1.69 shape factor. “Montalto di Castro 2” features a Weibull distribution with 6.75 m/s mean and 1.71 shape factor.

Figure 4. Wind speed distribution, Montalto di Castro

The most probable significant wave height in this site is 0.23 m, while the modal value of mean and peak wave periods are 3.34 s and 2.42 s; instead the mean wave height value is 0.64 m, with mean and peak wave periods of 4.0 s and 4.5 s respectively. The distribution of the joint conditions considering an averaging time of 1 hour are reported in the Figure below. The distribution of joint wind-wave misalignment per wind velocity is also reported in the figure below. In this site, the probability of recording a misalignment up to 90 degrees is higher than in other sites.

Figure 5. Sea states and wind-wave misalignment for the site “Montalto di Castro”. The colour map indicates the normalized occurrence frequency

4.3 Adriatic Sea

Although mostly not suitable for Floating wind projects, due to its shallow waters, the Adriatic Sea has proven attractive for project developers as it hosts more than one offshore wind project (<https://www.agnespower.com/>). The location selected within this report is 30 km off the coast of Emilia Romagna, with geographic coordinates 44.4296° N 12.6509° E. Wind speeds are low, and the Weibull distribution for this site features a shape factor of 1.61 and a mean of 5.20 m/s.

Figure 6. Wind speed distribution, Emilia Romagna

The most probable significant wave height in this site is 0.16 m, while the modal value of mean and peak wave periods are 2.72 s and 2.39 s; instead the mean wave height value is 0.49 m, with mean and peak wave periods of 3.3 s and 3.8 s respectively. The distribution of the joint conditions considering an averaging time of 1 hour are reported in the Figure below. The distribution of joint wind-wave misalignment per wind velocity is also reported in the figure below. This site shows a less intense average sea states than the other sites under analysis.

Figure 7. Sea states and wind-wave misalignment for the site “Romagna”. The colour map indicates the normalized occurrence frequency

4.4 Malaga

The sites referred to as “Malaga 1” and “Malaga 2” are installation sites located off the coast of Spain, near the city of Malaga. The geographic coordinates of the sites are reported in Tab. 1. Their position with respect to the city of Malaga and the coastal waters of Spain is shown in Fig. 2.

The wind speed distribution for the “Malaga 1” site features a mean of 8.078 m/s and a shape factor of 1.88. The Weibull distribution for “Malaga 2” features a mean of 8.44 m/s and a shape factor of 1.84. For this state the sea state data have not been available for the full period under analysis.

Figure 8. Wind speed distribution, Malaga

4.5 Sardinia

The coasts of Sardinia are considered suitable for Floating Wind Projects [6] due to the relatively high wind speed that can be typically found in this area. The area selected in this report is located 40 km from the coast to reduce the visual impact of the turbines [6]. This however, causes the offshore wind park to be located in deep waters. The Weibull distribution for this site features a shape factor of 1.61 and a mean of 5.20 m/s.

The most probable significant wave height in this site is 0.36 m, while the modal value of mean and peak wave periods are 4.0 s and 6.16 s; instead the mean wave height value is 1.13 m, with mean and peak wave periods of 5.3 s and 6.3 s respectively. The distribution of the joint conditions considering an averaging time of 1 hour are reported in the Figure below. The distribution of joint wind-wave misalignment per wind velocity is also reported in the figure below.

Figure 9. Wind speed distribution, Sardinia

Figure 10. Sea states and wind-wave misalignment for the site “Sardinia”. The colour map indicates the normalized occurrence frequency

4.6 Sicily

An installation site west of Sicily is also considered in the analysis [7]. This installation has been linked, due to its location to the “Tyrrhenian Link” project, an underwater cable project to link Sardinia, Sicily and the Italian peninsula [8]. The Weibull distribution for this site is characterized by a shape factor of 1.85 and a mean wind speed of 7.70 m/s.

Figure 11. Wind speed distribution, Sicily

The most probable significant wave height in this site is 0.46 m, while the modal value of mean and peak wave periods are 4.54 s and 5.16 s; instead the mean wave height value is 1.12 m, with mean and peak wave periods of 4.9 s and 5.6 s respectively. The distribution of the joint conditions considering an averaging time of 1 hour and the distribution of joint wind-wave misalignment per wind velocity are reported in the figure below.

Figure 12. Sea states and wind-wave misalignment for the site “Sicily”. The colour map indicates the normalized occurrence frequency

4.7 Naples

Another site being considered is Naples, which has already been featured in other projects to promote the opportunities offered by floating offshore wind power.

Figure 13. Wind speed distribution, Naples

The most probable significant wave height in this site is 0.18 m, while the modal value of mean and peak wave periods are 2.6 s and 1.83 s; instead the mean wave height value is 0.73 m, with mean and peak wave periods of 4.3 s and 5.0 s respectively. The distribution of the joint conditions considering an averaging time of 1 hour and the distribution of joint wind-wave misalignment per wind velocity are reported in the figure below.

Figure 14. Sea states and wind-wave misalignment for the site “Naples”. The colour map indicates the normalized occurrence frequency

5. Comparison of wind conditions in the installation sites

A comparison of the wind speed distributions at 100 meters above sea level for the sites in the present report is shown in Fig. 15. Distributions for IEC wind class III and IV that feature a shape factor of 2 and a mean wind speed of 7.5 and 6.0 m/s, respectively, as well as data relative to the “FINO 1” wind farm in the North Sea are shown for comparison. Wind speeds in the “Romagna” site in the Adriatic Sea are clearly lower than those in the other sites that are considered herein. The standard wind speed distribution that most resembles the conditions on the Italian coast is the IEC class IV distribution, as it features higher wind speeds than the Romagna site but lower than the Sicily, Sardinia and “Montalto di Castro” locations. If we focus on floating wind and exclude the “Romagna” distribution, Class III could represent a good approximation of the conditions in the different installation sites.

6. Comparison of sea states

The analysis of average sea states shows similar conditions among the sites with available wave data. We notice that higher waves are more probable in the Sicily and Sardinia sites while similar characteristics are found in sites of “Gulf of Lion” and “Romagna”.

This preliminary analysis will be further integrated with detailed and statistical analyses in the definition of the specific conditions to use in the design load cases after definition of the reference sites.

Figure 15: Comparison of the wind speed distributions for the sites in this report. (a) wind speed @100m above sea level and (b) wind speed at 170m above sea level. Wind speed at 100m is obtained from ERA5, while wind speed at 170m is scaled from 100m assuming wind-shear according to the power law (section 2, equation 1) with exponent 0.12.

Figure 15 Average significant wave height and peak period per wind velocity

7. Reference sites selection

Water depth is chosen as the primary criterion for selecting three representative sites that reflect the Mediterranean met-ocean conditions for defining the design load cases. In particular, waters deeper than 400 meters are excluded to facilitate a design of the Floating Offshore Wind Turbine (FOWT) where the mooring system does not pose a critical technological challenge. Therefore, although sites such as Malaga 1 and Malaga 2 present suitable wind resources in the Mediterranean Sea, they will be excluded due to the water depth that would result in complex mooring and anchor systems that may be critical to assess project sustainability and risks. On the other hand, the Ravenna site presents a wind resource that is significantly different from the rest of the sites surveyed, with a lower average and PDF shape factor. Additionally, the water depth at this site could also allow fixed-bottom foundations, although the selection criteria here assume conditions typical for FOWT in the Mediterranean Sea. Among the other sites, Gulf of Lion 1, Sicily, and Montalto di Castro 1 meet the selection criteria and are chosen as reference sites.

8. Conclusions

Based on this preliminary survey, derived using ERA5 reanalysis data, the standard IEC class that resembles a wide variety of installation sites in the Mediterranean most closely is IEC 61400-1 Class III.

The survey identified several sites in the Mediterranean suitable for offshore wind installations, selecting three reference sites: Gulf of Lion 1, Sicily, and Montalto di Castro 1. These sites were chosen considering the quality of wind resources and water depth, balancing wind quality and the technological complexity of mooring systems. The wind and wave conditions at the selected sites will be used to define the design load cases for floating wind turbines, adapting them to the specific local conditions.

9. References

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